

Improving Performance and Service Delivery in Higher Education through the Promotion of Quality Leadership, Commitment and Work Motivation by Utilizing Computerized System in the Era of Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract - This study examines how service leadership and affective commitment influence lecturer performance. The study also seeks to reveal how work motivation affects work performance; to understand how service leadership influences academic service quality, to point out how affective commitment influences service quality, to investigate how work motivation affects lecturer service quality, and to find out how lecturer performance affects academic service quality in Faculty of Education and Teacher Training (FIKP) of Universitas Lambung Mangkurat (UNLAM) Banjarmasin. This study used the explanatory research approach. The study population comprised of 205 people selected through proportionate stratified random sampling. The Slovin's formula was used in determining the sample and 136 people were sorted as the sample. Data was analyzed by the Partial Least Squares (PLS) of the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The results show a significant relationship between service leadership and lecturer performance in FKIP, UNLAM. Secondly, it was found that affective commitment does not have a significant impact towards lecturer performance. Thirdly, the results indicate that work motivation influences lecturer performance significantly. It was also found that service leadership influences the quality of academic service provided by the lecturer. Affective commitment was found as significantly

contributing to service quality, and work motivation was found to be significantly affecting service quality.

Index Terms - Service leadership, affective commitment; work motivation, lecturer performance, and academic service.

INTRODUCTION

The current condition of the Faculty of Education and Teacher Training at Universitas Lambung Mangkurat (UNLAM) reveals that lecturer performance and service quality are not good enough. This can be deduced from: a) the educational accreditation of the program, which is far from good (only 6 study programs are registered and 5 other accreditations have expired); b) The average face-to-face lecturing is below 75%; c) about 30.73% of the program's lecturers are bachelor's degree graduates; d) The average of lecturer promotion is every 4 years; e) 13.30% of the students took more than 1 year to finish their thesis; and f) there was a high number of students (12.91%) who took 5 years of study to finish college [1].

All the aspects mentioned above are the result of collective work of all the educational staffs, including the university head (service leadership) and all the lecturers (commitment and work motivation). This study's aims are a) to find out how service leadership influences work performance; b) to understand the influence of affective

commitment toward lecturer performance; c) to investigate work motivation's effect on lecturer performance; d) to reveal how service leadership influences service quality; e) to find out the relationship between affective commitment and service quality; f) to find a connection between work motivation and service quality; and g) to understand how work performance influences the quality of academic service.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

Previous studies have highlighted six main characteristics that reflect service leadership, namely empowering and developing employees, humility, authenticity, interpersonal acceptance, providing direction, and stewardship [2-8]. Based on these characteristics, it can be taken that service leadership refers to how the leaders guide and encourage their employees, how they can prioritize between personal matters, talent, and achievement, how their attitude reflects honesty and openness; the ability to understand and take good care of the employee; ensure that employees understand their jobs; being responsible not only for themselves but also for their fellow employees.

Meanwhile, the term service leadership in this context refers to how the university head empowers lecturers; encourages them to develop their skill; the ability to position their personal matters on the right track; act openly, treat all the lecturers equally; ensure that all lecturers understand their job; and being responsible for the outcomes under their service leadership [9-13].

In addition, there are three types of commitments which can increase lecturer's dedication toward the institution, namely affective, continuance, and normative commitment [14-18]. From all the types of commitments above, affective commitment is chosen in this study due to several considerations: a) this study focuses on psychological aspects of the lecturer regarding their commitment to the university which resulted happiness and satisfaction; b) The other commitments only emphasize the speculative aspects and norm consequences, which are considered as inappropriate for their job as a lecturer.

Affective commitment in this study can be referred to the dedication of the lecturers towards FKIP UNLAM, which gives them benefit in several elements, such as getting satisfying experiences and valuable things from their sincerity in doing their job. Furthermore, it can lead to a situation where they are willing to spend the rest of their career at FKIP UNLAM.

Maslow in [19] divides human needs into five stages known as the five hierarchy need of motivational theory. The theory covers physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization needs, ranking from the lowest to the highest need. Meanwhile, work motivation refers to the internal and external stimulation that makes individuals take or do something in order to fulfill their needs [20-24]. Working motivation in this study

refers to lecturer's motivation, resulting from the ability to fulfill their needs.

According to the Academic Workload Guidance of the Indonesian Department of Higher Education (PBKDEPTPT), work performance is specified in the Tri-dharma ('three pillars') of higher education [25-27]. In this study, work performance refers to the implementation of lecturers' main activity in carrying out the Tri-dharma of higher education that include the teaching field, research field, social service, and other supporting activities of the Tri-dharma of higher education.

On the other hand, Parasuraman et al [28], as cited in [29], explains that the SERQUAL method enables researchers to measure and evaluate the quality of the services through ten dimensions namely, tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, communication, credibility, security, competence, courtesy, understanding/knowing customers, and access. All the dimensions are then, specified into five different elements of service quality, which include tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

From the above insights, service quality can be defined as a customer's satisfaction towards the service, which is reflected through the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, and personnel ability to perform the promised service accurately, willingness to help customers, knowledge and courtesy of employees along with their persuading skills, and individualized attention accorded to customers.

Yet, service quality in this manner means the quality of the lecturing, which is seen through a lecturer's appearance during classes, their teaching skills, the willingness to help students outside the classroom, their persuading skills, and their attitude toward students during the class.

Based on the literature reviewed above, several hypotheses are made: a) Service leadership has significant impact on lecturer performance in FKIP, UNLAM Banjarmasin; b) Affective commitment gives significant impact toward lecturer performance; c) Lecturer performance in FKIP, UNLAM is influenced significantly by work motivation; d) Service leadership significantly affects service quality; e) There is a significant relation between affective commitment and service quality; f) There is a significant connection between work motivation and service quality; g) Lecturer performance in FKIP, UNLAM influence their service quality significantly.

RESEARCH METHOD

A research plan is a framework where relation among variables is conceptualized. Explanatory research is concerned with analyzing and describing the impact of each variable through testing the hypotheses. Since the aims of this study correspond with explanatory research, this method is employed as the analytical tool [30].

The variables included in this study are service leadership, affective commitment, work motivation, lecturer

performance, and service quality. Meanwhile, the study was conducted in Faculty of Education and Teacher Training (FKIP) UNLAM Banjarmasin.

Population means the general area of the research object/subject with characteristic. Population does not only refer to human being, but also to other things, such as objects and objects found in nature [31]. In this study, the population is all the lecturers of FKIP UNLAM Banjarmasin, with a total of 205 people consisting of 34 associate lecturers, 68 lecturers, 95 senior lecturers, and 8 professors.

Slovin formula is used to determine the sample of the research [32]. In this study, the sample includes 136 people out of 205. The respondents of the study are consisted of: a) 16 heads of study program to compile data regarding lecturer performance, 136 lecturers relate to service leadership variables; and 408 students relate to service quality point.

The five variables used in the study are, service leadership, affective commitment, work motivation, work performance, and service quality. These variables are classified into 3 different categories: a) independent variables which cover service leadership (X1), affective commitment (X2), and motivation (X3); b) intervening variables which include work performance (Y1); c) dependent or endogen variables, which covers service quality. In this study, data is obtained through questionnaire and documentation. The questionnaire was used to gather primary data, while documentation was used to collect secondary data. Primary data consisted of data from the respondents such as, the head of X study program, lecturers, and students, while secondary data consisted of evaluation data of the study program.

The purpose of gathering data from EPSBED is to ensure the reliability of the information used in the background of the study. The data was then, analyzed using the computer program package of PLS-SEM analysis. Considering the aims of the study, two classical analysis categorization is used, namely descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In the analysis, Inner Model (structural model) is used to test the hypotheses which illustrate the impact of each variable based on substantive theory.

FIGURE 1
CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK MODEL AFTER BOOTSTRAPPING

Inner model is employed through analyzing R-square value as goodness of fit model test. Besides, there is also significance test of each construct to see parameter coefficient value and the t-statistic value as illustrated in Figure I:

Hypotheses test is conducted through partial test and simultaneous test. The influence of one variable is considered as significant if the t-result > t-table, as explained in the following subsection.

Direct Effect: Direct effect refers to how independent variable influences dependent variable without the involvement of other variables. In this study, seven hypotheses belong to direct effect with t-result > t-table implied significant connection, and t-table = 1 as illustrated below.

Where: S = Sig
NS = Not Sig

FIGURE 2
CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK MODEL AFTER BOOTSTRAPPING

The above example points out the direct significant relation between exogen and endogen variables, and a non-significant relation between affective commitment and work performance.

TABLE I
HYPOTHESIS TEST RESULT (DIRECT)

Impact		Coefficient	t-result	Note
Service leadership	→ Work performance	0.351	2.300	Significant
Affective Commitment	→ Work performance	0.006	0.048	Not Significant
Work Motivation	→ Work performance	0.276	2.092	Significant
Service Leadership	→ Service Quality	0.232	2.068	Significant
Affective Commitment	→ Service Quality	0.237	2.494	Significant
Work motivation	→ Service Quality	0.240	2.219	Significant
Work performance	→ Service quality	0.191	2.067	Significant

The result of the analysis reveals that service leadership and work motivation have a significant influence on work performance, while affective commitment does not contribute significantly to work performance. Furthermore, the service leadership element, affective commitment, and work performance are influencing the service quality significantly.

The biggest coefficient track toward lecturer performance is service leadership (0.351), while the lowest is work motivation with (0.276). Meanwhile, affective commitment affects service quality with 0.237 points and lecturer performance gave a slight impact of 0.191 points as stated below:

Hypothesis 1: Service Leadership gives a significant impact towards Lecturer Performance in FKIP UNLAM Banjarmasin

The coefficient value reveals a relation between service leadership and work performance with 0.351 and t-result of 2.300. The value of t-result > t-table means that the first hypothesis is accepted and indicates a significant relation between two factors. The positive result of the coefficient value reflects the same aim of both factors, which indicates that the better the service leadership, the better performance lecturers give, and vice versa.

Hypothesis 2: Affective Commitment has a significant influence towards Lecturer Performance in FKIP UNLAM Banjarmasin

The coefficient value reveals a relation between affective commitment and lecturer performance with 0.006 and a t-result of 0.048. The value of the t-result < t-table, which means that the second hypothesis is ignored and shows a non-existence relation between two factors.

Hypothesis 3: Work Motivation has a significant influence towards Lecturer Performance in FKIP UNLAM Banjarmasin

The coefficient value reveals a relation between motivation and working performance with 0.276 and a t-result of 2.092. The value of the t-result > t-table meaning that the third hypothesis is accepted and indicates a significant relation between two factors. The positive result the of the coefficient value reflects the same aim of both factors, it

indicates that the higher their motivation, the better the performance they can provide.

Hypothesis 4: Service Leadership has a significant influence towards Service Quality in FKIP UNLAM Banjarmasin

The coefficient value reveals a relation between service leadership and service quality with 0.232 and a t-result of 2.068. The value of the t-result > t-table means that the fourth hypothesis is accepted and indicates a significant relation between two factors. The positive result of the coefficient value reflects the same aim of both factors, indicating that the better the service leadership, the better the service quality lecturers can provide.

Hypothesis 5: Affective Commitment has a significant influence on service quality in FKIP UNLAM Banjarmasin

The coefficient value reveals a relation between affective commitment and the service quality with 0.237 and a t-result of 2.494. The value of the result > t-table meaning that the fifth hypothesis is accepted and indicates a significant relation between two factors. The positive result of the coefficient value reflects the same aim of both factors, indicating that the better the commitment lecturers have, the better the service they can provide.

Hypothesis 6: Work motivation has a significant influence on service quality in FKIP UNLAM Banjarmasin

The coefficient value reveals a relation between work motivation and the service quality with 0.240 and a t-result of 2.219. The value of the t-result > t-table meaning that the sixth hypothesis is accepted and indicates a significant relation between two factors. The positive result of the coefficient value reflects the same aim of both factors, indicating that the higher the motivation, the better the service.

Hypothesis 7: Lecturer performance gives significant influence towards service quality in FKIP UNLAM Banjarmasin

The coefficient value reveals a relation between work performance and the service quality with 0.191 and t-result of 2.067. The value of the t-result > t-table meaning that the sixth hypothesis is accepted and indicates a significant relation between two factors. The positive result of coefficient value reflects the same aim of both factors, indicating that the higher lecturer performance, the better service they can provide and vice versa.

Indirect Effect: Indirect effect refers to how independent variables influence dependent variables through intervening variables, which in this case is lecturer performance. There are three different hypotheses regarding indirect effect: the service leadership variable, affective commitment variable, and work motivation toward quality of service.

TABLE II
INDIRECT EFFECT RESULT

Independent Variable	Intervening Variable	Dependent Variable	Coefficient	
Service leadership	Work performance	Quality	0.351x 0.191=	0.067
Affective Commitment	Work performance	Quality	0.006x 0.191=	0.001
Work Motivation	Work performance	Quality	0.276x 0.191=	0.053

The above table can be interpreted into several things: indirect effect of the service leadership has $0.067 = 6.7\%$ impact to the lecturer performance, affective commitment has $0.001 = 0.01\%$ impact, and work motivation gives $0.053 = 5.3\%$ contribution to work performance.

Total Effect: Total effect is the sum of direct and indirect effect as can be seen in Table 3.

TABLE III
TOTAL EFFECT

Independent Variable	Direct effect (a)	Indirect effect (b)	Total (a) + (b)	t-result
Service leadership	0.232	0.067	0.299	2.719
Affective commitment	0.237	0.001	0.238	2.625
Work motivation	0.240	0.053	0.293	2.931

Based on the result in Table 3, it can be said that: The value of the t-result is 2.719, which is $>$ t-table indicating a total significant effect on service leadership. Moreover, the result of total effect, which is 29.9%, indicates a positive influence through service quality. The value of the t-result of affective commitment is 2.625, which is $>$ t-table indicating a significant total impact. Moreover, the result of the total effect of 23.8% reveals a positive influence as a result of affective commitment. Following this, the value of t-result of 2.931 $>$ t-table indicates a total significant influence of motivation. In the Table 3, the motivation aspect is resulted 29.3% toward the quality service which means it has positive significant to the service.

The Goodness of fit model

The inner model refers to the structural test, which considers the R-square as goodness of fit model. The value of R-square reveals how big the influence was on dependent variables as summarized in the Table 4.

TABLE IV
GOODNESS OF FIT MODEL RESULT

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	R-square
Service leadership, affective commitment, and work motivation	Lecturer Performance	0.3292
Service leadership, affective commitment, and work motivation	Service Quality	0.5318

The 0.3292 value of the R-square indicates a 32.92% influence of independent variables towards dependent variables and a 67.8% influence on other variables. That R-square value also indicates a 32.92% influence of independent variables towards dependent variables and 67.8% influence on other variables.

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CONCLUSION

There are several conclusions which are drawn from the results of the analysis of this study's data. The service leadership aspect gives a significant influence on work performance of FKIP UNLAM lecturers. The positive coefficient indicates a similar direction of both elements, where a better the service leadership can lead to better performance.

The results do not reveal a significant impact given by affective commitment. It does not matter how big the commitment is, since lecturer performance does not depend on this aspect.

Work motivation has a significant impact on work performance. The higher the motivation, the better the work performance.

The service leadership aspect has an important role in the service quality provided by FKIP UNLAM lecturer. The positive coefficient implies how better service leadership can lead to better service. Moreover, through the work performance medium, service leadership aspects indirectly influence 6.7% of service quality.

The affective commitment aspect gives a significant impact on service quality. The positive result of the coefficient shows that better the commitment will eventually lead to better service provided by the staff. Moreover, indirectly, affective commitment contributes about 0.1% to the services.

Work motivation influences the quality of services in a significant way. The higher the motivation the better the services provided due to the positive coefficient between both aspects. Indirectly, work motivation also gives a 5.3% influence towards the service provided.

Similarly, lecturer performance gives a significant impact towards service quality in FKIP UNLAM. Based on the positive coefficient result of the analysis, work performance contributes about 19.1% to the final result of service quality.

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